

TERRESTRIAL MOLLUSKS FAMILY COCHLICOPIDAE AKHANGARAN BASIN

Saidov Madilkhan Azizkhanovich

PhD in Biological Sciences
Gulistan State University

Nurboeva Maftuna Yusupjonovna

2nd year master's student
Gulistan State University

maftuna.nurboeva.98@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10996931>

Annotation: high numbers, wide distribution, high species diversity, low mobility and insignificant ability to overcome geographical barriers, ease of collecting material and sensitive response to changes in the external environment make the group of terrestrial mollusks a convenient object of biogeographical and ecological research.

Keywords: Malacofauna, terrestrial mollusks, Palaearctic and Holarctic, xerophiles, complex, Central Asian, Mountain Asian, Western Asian

Over the past 20-25 years, a number of monographic works by K.K. Uvalieva, A. Pazilov, D. A. Azimov on the malacofauna of Central Asia, which provides information on its taxonomic structure, distribution, zoogeography and variability. However, the degree of study of terrestrial mollusks on the territory of Uzbekistan remains extremely uneven. And the malacofauna of the Akhangaran basin has been almost unstudied to date. The available data on terrestrial mollusks is fragmentary.

Families Cochlicopidae Pilsbry, 1900

1. Cochlicopa (Cochliopa) nitens (Gallenstein, 1852)

Material: more than 75 copies Southern slopes: surrounding villages: Urgaz, Shovoz, Ovzhazsay, along the ditches, among the grasses. On the right bank of the Shavgaz River, among the grasses.

Northern slopes: Surroundings of the village. Beshkul, Kuksarai, Sukak, along the ditches, among the grasses. On the right bank of the Zhakindik River, among thickets of grass.

The shell basically coincides with that described in the literature by A.A. Shileiko, A. Pazilov., D.A. Asimov. Measurement of adult specimens showed that it varies within the following limits: shell height 6.7 mm; large diameter 2.7 mm.

Ecology. Lives along ditches among grasses. Found in all zones.

Spreading. Europe, Caucasus, Central Asia.

Meaning. It is an intermediate host for *Brachylaemus aequans*.

Causes a disease called leukochloridosis, which affects the digestive systems of ruminant animals.

2. *Cochlicopa (Cochlicopa) lubricella* (Porro, 1838)

Material: 60 copies.

Southern slopes: Gushsay gorge, under stones among grasses, on the right bank of Dukentsay, among grasses. The gorge of the Kyzilcha river under stones, among grasses.

Northern slopes: Chatkal Nature Reserve along ditches, among grasses. On the right bank of the Shavasay River, among thickets of grass.

Our material corresponds to the published descriptions of A.A. Shileiko, A. Pazilov., D.A. Azimov, but is distinguished by a large dimensional variability of shells; within one population there are specimens with a shell height from 3.5 to 5.0 mm, a large diameter of 1.9-2.1 mm.

Ecology. It is found at an altitude of 1500 – 2200 m above sea level. Lives under stones among grasses.

Spreading. Europe (except for the North), Transcaucasia, Alai, Turkestan, Kuramin, Chatkal, Talas, Trans-Ili, Kungey, Tersky ranges, Dzungarian Alatau, Southern Altai.

Meaning. It is an intermediate host for *Varestrongylus pneumaticus*.

Causes a disease called leukochloridosis, which affects the digestive systems of ruminant animals.

3. *Cochlicopa (Cochliopa) lubrica* (Muller, 1774)

Material: more 100 copies.

Found together with the previous species.

The shell in all respects, except for size, corresponds to the literary data of A.A. Shileiko, A. Pazilov., D.A. Asimov. The dimensions of our collection of shells are: shell height 4.2-5.1 mm, large diameter 1.8-2.4 mm.

Ecology. Lives under stones among grasses.

Spreading. Europe, North-West Africa, Northern Asia, Transcaucasia, Iran, Northern China, North America, Tien Shan, Pamir-Alai.

Meaning. It is an intermediate host for *Leucochloridium macrostomum*.

Causes a disease called leukochloridosis, which affects the digestive systems of ruminant animals.

Literatures used:

1. Feruza Gaibnazarova, Nilufar Ruzikulova, Nargiza Safarova, Khilola Khakberdiyeva, and Ulugbek Musabekov "Conchological variation of widely common species of terrestrial mollusks of Uzbekistan" E3S Web of Conferences <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202449401021494> AEES2023

2. Feruza Gaibnazarova. Faunistic spectrum of terraneous mollusks of Uzbekistan and bordering territories E3S Web of Conferences 392, 02040 (2023) <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202339202040RSE-II-2023>
3. Pazilov A., Gaibnazarova F., Saidov M. Patterns of vertical distribution of terrestrial mollusks of Uzbekistan and adjacent territories. Tashkent: Fan, 2014. B-11
4. Pazilov A., Gaibnazarova F. Geographical variability of conchological features of the terrestrial mollusk *Pseudonapaeus aptechus* // Proceedings of the VIII International Scientific and Practical Conference.- Krasnodar, 2014.- pp. 128-130.
5. Gaibnazarova F. The nature of the variability of the signs of the sexual apparatus of *Pseudonapaeus albiplicata* From the Chatkal, Kuraminsky Ridges - Guliston Davlat Aksborotnomasi University, No. 3. 2015 B-21
6. Gaibnazarova F., Pazilov A. On the fauna of terrestrial mollusks (gastropods, Puymonata) of the Kugitangtau ridge. Proceedings of the conference "Ecology, Evolution and systematics of animals" November 13-16, 2012 B-13-16
7. Gaibnazarova F., Pazilov A. Conchological variability of terrestrial mollusks *Nanosignals of gibbulinopsis* of Turkestan and Zarafshan ridges. Zoological studies of the regions of Russia and adjacent territories materials for the III International Scientific Conference. Nizhny Novgorod - 2014.
8. Pazilov A. Gaibnazarova F., Karimova H. Complexes of terrestrial mollusks in various biotopes of the Zarafshan ridge JOURNALNX - Interdisciplinary peer-reviewed journal ISSN: 2581-4230, Website: journalnx.com, June 18-19, 2020.
9. Pazilov A., Gaibnazarova F., Karimova x alien species *Monacha carthusiana* (Mollusks, gastropods, pulmonary) as a new intermediate host of the nematode *cystocaulus ocreatus* in Uzbekistan. Naukoviy visnik Uzhhorod universitetu Seriya Biologiya, Vipusk 40, 2016: B 83-85.
10. Gaibnazarova F. The nature of the variability of the signs of the sexual apparatus of *Pseudonapei albiplicate* from the Chatkal and Kuramin ranges. Biological Sciences of Kazakhstan No. 3, 2014.
11. Gaibnazarova F. Biological diversity of terrestrial mollusks of the Surkhan-Sherabad valley and its surrounding mountain ranges // Naukovi zapiski Ternopil National Pedagogical University im. Volodimira Gnatyuk. Ser. Biologiya Ternopil: TNPU, 2012. - Vip. 2 (51), Spec. vip. : Moluski: results, problems and prospects doslizhen. - pp. 54-57- - Bibliogr. in kinci art.
12. Pazilov A., Gaibnazarova F. Conchological variability of the terrestrial mollusk *Signature of gibbulinopsis* from the Baysuntau, Kugitangtau and

- Babatag ridges. "Ecology, evolution and systematics of animals". Ryazan -2012
Materials of the international scientific and practical conference
13. Pazilov A., Gaibnazarova F. Species composition and variability of terrestrial mollusks of the genus Cochlicopa of Uzbekistan and adjacent territories / Ecological features of biological diversity: proceedings of the 5th International Conference - Hadjent, 2013 - pp.96-97.
17. Pazilov A., Gaibnazarova F. Population variability of conchological features of the terrestrial mollusk Pseudonapei secalin from the Turkestan ridge // Theory and practice of current research. Materials of the VI International Scientific and Practical Conference.- Krasnodar, 2014. pp. 45-47.18.
15. Goibnazarova F., Pazilov A. Conchological variability of terrestrial mollusk Nanosignals of gibbulinopsis in Turkestan and Zarafshan ridges//Zoological studies of the regions of Russia and adjacent territories. III International Scientific Conference.- Nizhny Novgorod, 2014. pp.35-37.
- 16.F Gaibnazarova. A variety of dry shellfish is common in the regions of Uzbekistan and adjacent to it. Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology 25(6), 2828-2834
17. Gaipnazarova Feruza. Distribution of land snail by vertical zones and biotopes of Pseudonapaeus species in Fergana, Chatkal and Kurama mountain range // European science review. – 2016. – No. 1-2. – pp. 3-4
18. A Pazilov, F Gaibnazarova, M Saidov - Tashkent. from "Fan", Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2014
19. Gaibnazarova F. Geographical variability of conchological characteristics of the terrestrial mollusk Pseudonapaeus aptechus // modern science: development trends. Proceedings of the VIII International Scientific and Practical Conference. – 2014. – P. 128-130.

